

TECHNOLOGIES FOR TRAINING FUTURE VISUAL ARTS TEACHERS TO FORM ELEMENTS OF ARTISTIC THINKING IN SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Abstract. *This article provides information that aesthetic perception is a product of artistic thinking.*

Keywords: *perception, emotional and aesthetic, artistic and aesthetic, thinking, image, abstract, logical, perception, deduction.*

Lectures are the main form of training future art teachers for pedagogical activities. In addition, pedagogic practices, special seminars, practical trainings and independent work of students are organized to provide theoretical and practical training of future visual arts teachers.

In preparing future teachers of fine arts for the formation of artistic thinking in schoolchildren, along with specialized subjects, educational subjects of the general pedagogical category have special opportunities. General methodological and pedagogical rules, general pedagogical directions, measures of students' readiness for pedagogical activity, principles, factors, conditions, system, stages of the pedagogical process, its general content, "technology, form, methods and the formation of elements of artistic thinking in the process of assimilation in their activities" ways to expand their capabilities will also be shown."

In order for the process of teaching future art teachers to form the elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren to be effective and to achieve positive results, it is appropriate to define a pedagogical work system that includes educational content, technologies, methods and methodology. Special attention is paid to the practical application of pedagogical knowledge.

It is necessary to rely on the following rules, that is, "future teachers of fine arts:

- development of a special methodology for preparing schoolchildren for the formation of elements of artistic thinking;
- formation of professional motivational need for formation of artistic thinking among schoolchildren;
- teaching schoolchildren professional skills that ensure a consistent approach to the process of forming elements of artistic thinking;
- introducing students to the possibilities of artistic perception of aesthetic views in the content of events;
- equipping with the features of the pedagogical process aimed at forming the elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren and the technology of its organization;
- introducing the requirements for forming a well-rounded person, which is a priority in the educational policy of our country;
- preparation for ensuring the priority of national and universal values in the education of general education schools;
- arming schoolchildren with international experiences that serve to improve the process of forming elements of artistic thinking;

- teaching to ensure the harmony of the educational process;
- achieving that schoolchildren rely on the normative foundations of the problem in the process of forming elements of artistic thinking;
- such as instilling advanced experiences that serve to prepare schoolchildren for the formation of elements of artistic thinking.

In order to prepare future teachers of fine arts for pedagogical activities aimed at forming elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren, it is necessary to ensure the priority of a number of directions in the process of higher education:

- Future art teachers should have the following professional competences.
- "to be able to clearly determine the purpose of the process of formation of elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren";
- to be able to ensure consistency and expediency of means of formation of elements of artistic thinking among schoolchildren;
- "to have tendencies to develop professionally and personally;
- to be able to take into account their age characteristics and development opportunities in the formation of elements of artistic thinking among schoolchildren";
- to be able to implement the approach focused on the personality of the student in the process of pedagogical practice;
- adherence to the principle of the integrity of the educational process in forming the elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren;
- to ensure the interdependence of emotional perception and practical activities in the formation of elements of artistic thinking of students;
- to be able to creatively approach the process of formation of elements of artistic thinking among schoolchildren, to know well the technologies of organizing this process;
- to acquire the skills of theoretical and practical preparation for extracurricular work on the formation of elements of artistic thinking in students;

The following criteria are used to determine the effectiveness of the process of preparing future visual arts teachers for the formation of elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren:

- to know the principles of formation of elements of artistic thinking of students, which are a priority in educational policy;
 - to know the professional and personal importance of preparing future visual arts teachers to form elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren;
 - to realize that visual art classes are an important means of forming elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren.
- For this purpose, it is assumed that the future teachers of fine arts should master the following:
- know the teaching methods, methods and tools that serve to form the elements of artistic thinking in students in fine art classes and be able to use them appropriately in pedagogical activity;
 - "psychological-pedagogical approach to educational situations that serve to form elements of artistic thinking in students in fine arts classes; to be able to reveal the mentality and personal qualities of students according to their individual characteristics;
 - to know the criteria for evaluating the level of formation of elements of artistic thinking among schoolchildren";

– future fine art teachers should know the content, theoretical and practical foundations, pedagogical system of the process, used technologies, tools of formation of elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren in the conditions of education outside the classroom.

Indicators such as the ability of future fine art teachers to conduct pedagogical research on the formation of elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren, to know how to improve their skills, to be able to plan methodological and pedagogical work in this field are also an important factor in assessing their level of readiness for professional and pedagogical activities. In this process, it is important that students feel the need for independent education and self-improvement. Therefore, the technological approaches used in the preparation of the future art teacher for school education should be in accordance with the qualities formed on the basis of the above-mentioned criteria.

A number of principles are followed in the preparation of future visual arts teachers for the formation of elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren. They are:

- "to have a comprehensive content and methods of the process of preparing future teachers of fine arts to form elements of artistic thinking in students";
- compatibility;
- communicativeness;
- such as the correlation between theory and practice.

Ensuring the success of the process of preparing future teachers of fine arts to form elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren depends on a number of interrelated factors. Among these factors, the composition of artistic thinking, feelings, emotions, personal views, the social and pedagogical situation encouraging artistic thinking, professional and personal knowledge and inclinations that serve to form artistic thinking, and the organization that serves to implement artistic education. - includes pedagogical conditions. At the same time, prospective plans made by students for the formation of artistic thinking in students, their knowledge of the education of artistic thinking, and the ability to organize a pedagogical process aimed at forming the elements of artistic thinking in students. The level of students' assimilation of technologies that serve to educate students artistically in the process of extracurricular education, their ability to choose and prepare demonstrative and illustrative tools that serve to form elements of artistic thinking, innovative methods, intellectual-creative, professional, methodical knowledge aimed at creating elements of artistic thinking, it is also possible to include such things as their communicative skills, their desire to learn independently, and their evaluations of activities aimed at forming elements of artistic thinking in students.

There are also a number of conditions for preparing future fine arts teachers to form artistic thinking in schoolchildren:

– preparing future teachers of fine arts for pedagogical activities aimed at forming elements of artistic thinking in students by providing them with a complex of special knowledge related to the formation of elements of artistic thinking in students as the main subjects of the higher education process;

– "to ensure that the future teachers of fine arts have sufficient knowledge and practical skills about the psychological and pedagogical features of the process as an important professional competence for preparing the elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren";

– in the process of pedagogical practice, to achieve that the future teachers of fine arts can express themselves creatively, professionally and personally in the implementation of methodical works aimed at forming the elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren;

– "encouraging the pedagogical work and innovative methods used by future fine art teachers during pedagogical practice aimed at forming the elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren";

"Giving future fine arts teachers lectures on the issue of formation of elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren", writing essays on the topic and organizing various events is one of the important indicators that determine professional readiness for pedagogical activities aimed at forming elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren.

The process of preparing future teachers of fine arts to form elements of artistic thinking in schoolchildren should be manifested as a unique pedagogical system. This process is expressed in the following.

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